

The discussion about the school practice of language analysis in the dialogic perspective /

Discussão sobre a prática escolar de análise linguística em perspectiva dialógica

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Received: 07 sept. 2022. **Approved:** 12 set. 2022.

How to cite:

NEVES, Herbertt. LIMA, Evanielle Freire. GOMES Lindiane Maria. OLIVEIRA, Larissa Evelyn Santos. The discussion about the school practice of language analysis in the dialogic perspective. *Revista Letras Raras*, v. 11, n. 3, p. 431-437, oct. 2022. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8160700>

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PEREIRA, Rodrigo Acosta; COSTA-HÜBES, Terezinha da Conceição (Orgs.). *Prática de análise linguística nas aulas de língua portuguesa*. São Carlos: Pedro & João, 2021. 529 p.

The theme of the Linguistic Analysis Practice (LAP) has become part of the discussions in mother tongue teaching in Brazil since the 1980s, and it is still present in Applied Linguistics nowadays. These more than 30 years, however, have not yet effectively established LAP as a pedagogical practice in Portuguese classes. The doubts that teachers have are numerous, especially when working with grammar, one of the possible aspects to be addressed in LAP, but not the only one. Another issue that also involved the topic was the scarcity of reference works designed exclusively to discuss it. To a large extent, when mentioning this notion in articles or separate chapters of books, the author always referred to texts written by Geraldi (1984) or Mendonça (2006), responsible, respectively, for founding the discussion in Brazil and expanding its dissemination among the teaching audience.

More recently, new works have emerged with the main objective of discussing LAP, its principles and proposals for application in the language class. It is in this context that the book *Practice of linguistic analysis in Portuguese language classes*, organized by Rodrigo Acosta Pereira and Terezinha da Conceição Costa-Hübes and published by Editora Pedro & João (2021), emerges. Organized in 4 parts, the work has 1 introduction and 15 chapters. In the first part, the historical course of LAP notion is discussed. In the second part, the main epistemological and theoretical-methodological principles that guide the notion of LAP are analyzed. In the third part, the discussion about the LAP return in the Common National Curricular Base (BNCC), based on the notion of linguistic/semiotic analysis, is developed. In the fourth and last part, didactic elaborations based on LAP are reported and discussed.

In the chapter *The Theoretical Epistemology Birth of Linguistic Analysis Practice: 80s and 90s*, Polato and Menegassi carry out reading movements that expose the construction and the subsequent and paradoxical silencing of the theme in the country. The analysis was based on an overview of works that supported the notion of LAP, published in Brazil during the 1980s and 1990s. The text ends with dialogue perspectives between LAP and the language of the Bakhtin Circle dialogical perspective, which will guide most of the discussions proposed by the other authors of the book.

The chapter *The Linguistic Analysis Practice: emergence, re-enunciations, scopes and productivity of the concept* aims to present LAP from the language teaching and learning

perspective, theoretically supported by the dialogical conception of language and the subject. For this purpose, Rosângela Hammes Rodrigues highlights the emergence of the LAP concept as a reactive action to the present language teaching traditional movement. When referring to the three basic units of Portuguese teaching, according to the linguistic analysis concept, as proposed by Geraldi (1984), the author makes an interesting association with the traditional *trivium* of the disciplines Rhetoric, Poetics and Grammar. The author emphasizes that the current proposal carries out an organic articulation that aims to achieve language practices domain through reflection on language in social interaction. This association allows us to understand why, in a certain way, there are still discourses, in the Academy and in Basic Education, that reinforce the linguistic analysis concept as a mere nomenclature change.

The chapter *About the language analysis: considerations in Bakhtin and Voloshinov* opens part 2 of the book. This article reintroduces the discussions proposed by Bakhtin and Voloshinov about the enunciation concept based on the analysis of selected excerpts from two important works, part III of *Marxism and Philosophy of Language: Fundamental Problems of the Sociological Method in the Science of Language*, by Voloshinov (2006) [1929]), and Bakhtin's *Speech Genres* (2003 [1979]). According to Pereira and Costa-Hübes, the authors of the article, the objective is to search in these works orientations, principles and forwardings to the linguistic analysis work based on a sociological bias of an enunciative-discursive basis. Although the article proposal is to review the considerations made by Voloshinov and Bakhtin, we noticed the authors great autonomy to explain the concepts presented in the works available in analysis.

In the chapter *The practice of linguistic analysis in an alteritarian dialogical conception of education*, the authors Sobral and Giacomelli advocate a pedagogical process that considers interaction as a central element of the student-teacher relation. In this process, the teacher would act as a more experienced pair, responsible for organizing the teaching methods. The text contributes to the LAP discussion from a dialogical perspective when it explains that this practice should start from the study of the meaning effects produced by the language resources present in the text materiality. It considers above all, the enunciative project, that corresponds, among others aspects, to the interlocutor responsiveness, to the social and historical dimensions, to the intonation and appreciative valuation of the words in the utterance.

The integrated chapter *The discourse genres as integrating elements for/in reading, listening, textual production and linguistic analysis classes: theoretical-methodological accessories* organizes the discussion in two different moments. The first refers to the theoretical questions that

serve as foundation for a discursive-enunciation analysis proposal through the work with the genres in a Dialogical Studies of Language perspective. In the second part, the discussion starts to have methodological forwardings, which stand out the possibilities of LAP anchored in the discourse genres, as the “guiding questions for the texts-utterances analysis”. Finally, the article presents the steps for working with language practices. From these steps, we highlight the first one, which quotes the research for references that support theoretically the work with genres. In our view, this stage ensures that LAP does not become just an intuitive and sometimes improvised work, but makes it theoretically and methodologically supported.

The chapter *Valorative epilinguistic activities in linguistic analysis practices from a dialogical perspective* points to language activities as essential to LAP, being an epilinguistic activity considered the fundamental stem for dialogical work (FRANCHI, 1987; GERALDI, 1991). The article presents a discussion about the epilinguistic activities development on an valuating level, that is, activities that consider the fact that “there is no discourse devoid of judgment” (POLATO; MENEGASSI, 2021, p. 187). In addition to linguistic choices, the authors affirm that the utterances construction and understanding involve aspects such as thematic, dialogical relationships, chronotopic valuations, social voices and intonations and valuations attributed to the genre.

The chapter *Linguistics analysis practices, modalization and referencing: expanding and connecting teaching objects*, by Márcia Mendonça, mentions the teaching objects incorporation, like cohesion and language variation, the integration between teaching axes and reading repertory diversification as signs of progress in the renovation process in the Portuguese language teaching. According to the text, this innovation, in turn, is tensioned in the fields of public policies and the academic one. In addition, there is a criticism regarding the lecture teaching model as a characteristic of what the author names as *the school form*, which keeps language teaching close to tradition.

The chapter that starts the third part of the book, entitled *The linguistic analysis practice in BNCC: a dialogical analysis of skills*, proposes to analyze the abilities related to the axis of linguistic/semiotic analysis in order to investigate to what extent these skills approach or distance themselves from the language dialogical theory. To that end, Clerisi recaptures the issues discussed in the previous articles, as the utterances notion as a unit of the language to be analyzed and the subjects social participation. She does that through discourses in interaction situations, considering the valuations and the different fields of action in which these speeches transit. By

presupposing what could be found in the analysis of skills, the author highlights the possibility of the existence of two discourses called in the text as the discourse of tradition and the discourse of change. The discourse of tradition is related to the word mechanization, evidenced by the metalanguage exhausting practice. The discourse of change is related to the subjective and complex language capable of promoting social changes. The research concludes that these discourses coexist in the abilities aimed at LAP highlighted in BNCC. Thus, this text dialogues with a recurring perception that the BNCC does not assume, as it indicates, a totally enunciative posture for the language teaching.

The text *Linguistic Analysis Practices in BNCC: constitutive and marked heterogeneity in the discourse*, developed by Kraemer and Costa-Hübes, propounds “a discursive analysis [...] of the postulations about the Linguistic Analysis Practice in BNCC” (KRAEMER; COSTA HÜBES, 2021, p. . 283). For this purpose, the authors focus on the discursive organization of the document to assess at what moments the treatment given to language teaching, when mentioning LAP, approaches the postulations defended by the dialogical perspective and at what moments they distance themselves from it. It is evident that the document is organized under two perspectives, one more interactional and the other more structural. The authors highlight that this conflicting view in the document reveals a tendency to maintain a structuralist bias for the Portuguese language teaching, since most of the methodological guidelines are centered on “automatizing practices of elements identification and grammatical categories” (KRAEMER; COSTA-HÜBES, 2012, p. 319).

Still within the scope of the BNCC, Giovani develops the work *BNCC: a linguistic/semiotic practice analysis in literacy*, in which will be presented an activity proposal applied for a child in the writing and reading acquisition period. The proposition can be replicated by other teachers who work in 1st Year classes, since, as the author highlights, “[in the document] It even lacks examples and proposals for prototypical activities” (GIOVANI, 2021 p. 325). In the author's words, “The BNCC does not provide paths and/or examples of how the teacher can work. What we did here was precisely an exercise of what could be done” (GIOVANI, 2021, p.343). Although we recognize the BNCC limitations in its general proposal and in several specific points, we disagree with the idea that it needs to indicate examples of activity, due to the nature of the document.

The chapter *Linguistic analysis: from grammar to the meaning senses*, by Rodrigues Franco and Rohling, closes the Part 3 of the work with the reflection about the challenges faced by many teachers in the work, in Portuguese language classes, with the grammatical aspects considering the dialogical character of the language. In an effort to assess the current approach of

the work with the linguistic elements, after the BNCC publication, the authors use as their investigation object six lesson plans available in a digital platform that are announced to be in accordance with the document in the linguistic/semiotic axis. The studied samples evidence that, despite there was an attempt to work the genres in an integrated way (considering the linguistic and paralinguistic elements), the results, in the authors' opinion, “proved to be insufficient, in reference to the approach of activities with the focus in the linguistic analysis, more specifically with regard to the meaning effects” (RODRIGUES; FRANCO; ROHLING, 2021, p. 379).

The fourth part of the work is introduced by the chapter *Language practices in Portuguese language classes in basic education: reading and linguistic analysis*, by Pereira e Costa-Hübes. In the first part of the work, discussions are held on the concepts of interaction, discourse, utterance, discourse genres, human activity scopes, general plasticity, responsive understanding of genres and ideology from the perspective of dialogism. These concepts structure the basis for the methodological proposal suggested by the authors for working with genres made up of verbal and visual elements. Pereira and Costa-Hübes reiterate the importance of analyzing discourse genres in their double dimension: the extraverbal and the verbal and visual, reiterating the dialogical vision of the work.

In the article *Theoretical-methodological proposal of linguistic analysis from a dialogical perspective to work with the pronoun*, developed by Ohuschi and Menegassi, the authors are based on an activity proposed in the Portuguese Language Olympiad material for the literary memory genre. Ohuschi and Menegassi note that in the material it is not considered the “language style as a constitutive element of written discourses” (OHUSCHI; MENEGASSI, 2021, p. 420). For this reason, they suggest a dialogical approach focused on the analysis of pronouns usage within the texts proposed in the support material. It is a way of highlighting not only the presence of the narrator - a central element in the construction of the literary memory genre -, but also its style, since the pronouns “mark the narrator's valuing positioning [...]” (OHUSCHI; MENEGASSI, 2021, p. 440).

In the text *Linguistic reading/analysis practices with comic strips in elementary school: a didactic and pedagogical proposal*, Fuza and Ritter develop a didactic proposal for working with the comic strip genre in the 6th grade. When dealing with aspects related to gender, Fuza and Ritter pay attention to the fact that all elements that are part of the comic strip are relevant to the meanings construction. Starting with a didactic proposal, the authors choose a strip of the character Armandinho and develop a sequence of questions that firstly explore aspects related to the social

dimension of the genre and, secondly, the verbal-visual. According to the authors, this type of activity “instruments the student-reader for the analytical reading of the enunciated text” (FUZA; RITTER, 2021, p. 476). We believe that the script developed in this chapter is essential for the training of teachers who want to consciously carry out LAP in their classes.

Part 4 ends with the article *Three drops of poetry: the linguistic analysis practice in a didactic proposal with the Brazilian children's haiku genre*, by Lunardelli. After the theoretical grounding presentation, the author reserves a substantial space of her work to present the historical origins of the haiku genre and its introduction into Brazilian culture, revealing the contact and distancing points of the Japanese and Brazilian versions. From then on, Lunardelli presents a didactic proposal addressed to the work with reading and linguistic analysis based on the haiku genre. The suggested activity was made based on the sociological model developed by the Circle and revisited by Rodrigues (2005) and Costa-Hübes (2015), which guides two types of analysis: the first, centered on social aspects of the genre, and the second, centered on aspects verbal-visuals.

Due to the aspects that were presented about all the chapters of this monumental work, we recognize its importance for the LAP discussion in Brazil, mainly because of its exhaustion nature in working possibilities with the theme, for the historical aspects and grounding to the didactic applications. Owing to its volume and originality as a work with a central LAP thematic, besides the relevance to the approach of the theme, we recommend its reading and its adoption in initial and continuing training courses for language teachers.